

Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie

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CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas
DOI/ 10.5281/zenodo.10001231

CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas

Programa de Pós-Graduação em Controladoria e Finanças
Empresariais

NORMA OU MARCO REGULATÓRIO

RESPOSTA À AUDIÊNCIA PÚBLICA - DISCUSSION PAPER
AND COMMENT LETTERS: LEASE LIABILITY IN A SALE AND
LEASEBACK

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Como referenciar:

Geron, C. M S; Formigoni, H; Farias, K. T. R.; Segura, L C.; Nishimura, P. S; Lioi, L. M.; Ferreiras, E.B.; Pinto, M. J. T. , Grecco, M. C. P. (2021). Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback. Norma ou Marco Regulatório. PPGCFTG da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie. Grupo de Estudos em IFRS. DOI/ 10.5281/zenodo.10001231

Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas

Linha de Pesquisa: Finanças, regulação contábil e tributária

Projeto de extensão: Grupo de Estudos em IFRS

Produto Técnico-Tecnológico: Norma ou marco regulatório

Demanda espontânea: resposta à consulta pública da Fundação IFRS.

Organização: Demanda da Fundação IFRS, produzido pelo Grupo de Pesquisa em IFRS da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie

Descrição do PPT: Resposta à consulta pública da Fundação IFRS, referente à alteração da norma IFRS 15 - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback.

Divulgação da Produção: A resposta à consulta pública foi enviada como resposta ao questionamento da Fundação IFRS. Sendo esta resposta um relatório derivado de um grupo de discussão e pesquisa, está disponível na plataforma Zenodo.

Aderência (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. O relatório técnico é resultado de uma ampla discussão de normas contábeis internacionais desenvolvida pelo grupo de pesquisa em IFRS, consistindo em um resultado de formação de pessoas (alunos de graduação e pós graduação) e também proposições técnicas que podem afetar a todas as organizações.

Impacto Potencial: Médio. O resultado desta resposta técnica resultará em alterações das normas contábeis internacionais com potencial de impacto para todas as empresas no mundo que adotam o IFRS.

Impacto Realizado: Médio. O impacto de uma alteração de norma deve ser observado no futuro, com a implementação das sugestões feitas por esse grupo de pesquisa. Dessa forma, só será possível medir o impacto na efetiva implementação das alterações sugeridas.

Inovação (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Média. Uma alteração de norma contábil internacional sobre *Leasing* e *leaseback* é uma inovação derivada de discussões para inserir nas normas a prática que já ocorre nas empresas. Portanto, a implementação efetiva desta norma sugere uma inovação para a área contábil e de produção de informações confiáveis para a estas entidades.

Complexidade (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Média. O produto requer um conhecimento técnico bastante abrangente em normas contábeis para que seja elaborado uma resposta técnica e cujo tema foi debatido em professores, alunos de mestrado e doutorado com diversas áreas de conhecimento técnico empresarial. Dessa forma, entende-se que a complexidade deste produto é média.

Aplicabilidade (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. Aplicabilidade para todas as empresas.

Abrangência Potencial (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. A norma terá aplicabilidade em todo o território nacional e internacional.

Abrangência realizada (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. A norma terá aplicabilidade em todo o território nacional e internacional.

Replicabilidade (Restrita, Irrestrita ou Escalável): Irrestrita

Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback

RESUMO

A Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie e a “Associação Nacional dos Executivos de Finanças, Administração e Contabilidade” - ANEFAC agradecem a oportunidade de responder ao Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback. No seu programa de pós-graduação profissional em Controladoria e Finanças Empresariais, a Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie estabeleceu um grupo de estudo sobre Normas Internacionais de Contabilidade. Um dos seus objetivos é discutir e apresentar propostas para consulta pública aos órgãos que definem as normas. A ANEFAC é uma entidade empenhada no aprimoramento e desenvolvimento profissional dos associados e executivos. Compartilha experiências profissionais, constrói relacionamentos e incentiva a pesquisa e a educação continuada em questões de finanças, gestão e contabilidade. Nossas respostas são baseadas na opinião do grupo de trabalho composto por profissionais e acadêmicos da área contábil.

Palavras-chave: Leaseback, norma, CPC 06

Response to Public Consultation: Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback

ABSTRACT

Mackenzie Presbyterian University and the “Associação Nacional dos Executivos de Finanças, Administração e Contabilidade” - ANEFAC appreciate the opportunity to respond to the Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback. In its professional postgraduate program in Accounting and Corporate Finance, Mackenzie Presbyterian University established a study group on International Accounting Standards. One of its objectives is to discuss and present proposals to standard-setting bodies’ public consultation. Anefac is a body engaged in the improvement and professional development of our associates and executives. We share professional experience, build relationships, and encourage research and continuing education in finance, management, and accounting issues. Our responses are based on the opinion of the working group composed of accounting professionals and academics.

Keywords: Leaseback, standards, IFRS 16

Como referenciar:

Geron, C. M S; Formigoni, H; Farias, K. T. R.; Segura, L C.; Nishimura, P. S; Lioi, L. M.; Ferreiras, E.B.; Pinto, M. J. T. , Grecco, M. C. P. (2021). Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback. Norma ou Marco Regulatório. PPGCFTG da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie. Grupo de Estudos em IFRS. DOI/ 10.5281/zenodo.10001231

Carta Apresentada ao IFRS em 29/03/2021

March 29, 2021.

International Accounting Standards Board
Columbus Building
7 Westferry Circus
Canary Wharf
London

Reference: Discussion Paper and comment letter: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback

Mackenzie Presbyterian University and the “Associação Nacional dos Executivos de Finanças, Administração e Contabilidade” - ANEFAC appreciate the opportunity to respond to the Discussion Paper and comment letters: Lease Liability in a Sale and Leaseback.

In its professional postgraduate program in Accounting and Corporate Finance, Mackenzie Presbyterian University established a study group on International Accounting Standards. One of its objectives is to discuss and present proposals to standard-setting bodies’ public consultation.

Anefac is a body engaged in the improvement and professional development of our associates and executives. We share professional experience, build relationships, and encourage research and continuing education in finance, management, and accounting issues.

Our responses are based on the opinion of the working group composed of accounting professionals and academics.

The authors of this document are Cecília Moraes Santostaso Geron, Kelly Teixeira Rodrigues Farias, Patrícia Satomi Nishimura, Lucas Molina Lioi, Liliane Cristina Segura, Henrique Formigoni, Érica Borges Ferreira, Murillo José Torelli Pinto, Leni Regina Segura, Marta Cristina Pelucio Grecco.

Yours sincerely,

Cecília Moraes Santostaso Geron
Professor at postgraduate program in Accounting and Corporate Finance
Mackenzie Presbyterian University
Director of International Accounting Standards at Anefac

Relatório apresentado à Consulta Pública

Questions for respondents

Question 1—Measurement of the right-of-use asset and lease liability arising in a sale and leaseback transaction (paragraphs 100(a)(i), 100A and 102B of the [Draft] amendment to IFRS 16)

The [Draft] amendment to IFRS 16 Leases applies to sale and leaseback transactions in which, applying paragraph 99 of IFRS 16, the transfer of the asset satisfies the requirements to be accounted for as a sale of the asset. The [Draft] amendment proposes:

- (a) to require a seller-lessee to determine the initial measurement of the right-of-use asset by comparing the present value of the expected lease payments, discounted using the rate specified in paragraph 26 of IFRS 16, to the fair value of the asset sold (paragraph 100(a)(i));
- (b) to specify the payments that comprise the expected lease payments for sale and leaseback transactions (paragraph 100A); and
- (c) to specify how a seller-lessee subsequently measures the lease liability arising in a sale and leaseback transaction (paragraph 102B).

Do you agree with this proposal? Why or why not? If you disagree with the proposal, please explain what you suggest instead and why.

The Research Group of Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie and ANEFAC prepared an event to present this document's questions to Brazil's market professionals and asked their opinion. Around 40 professionals participated in the event. The answers below are based on these professionals' responses and the study group's views formed by professors and graduate students from Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie and professionals from Anefac.

We agree with the inclusion of paragraphs 100 A and 102 B that detail the leased asset's measurement requirements in the case of leaseback and the measurement of the liability for these cases. We believe that the best detail helps understand how professionals should perform calculations and accounting records in their day-to-day practice.

It was not clear to the professionals we contacted the reason for the existence of different rules for the initial measurement of lease assets and liabilities compared to the lease in the leaseback case. In the first case, there is no comparison between the present value and the fair value of the asset (paragraph 26 in the pronouncement). In the second case, which deals with a leaseback, the asset's fair value is compared with the contract's present value. This different treatment for two types of lease does not seem clear to users and preparers of accounting information.

The argument that the previous treatment does not reflect a leaseback transaction's economic essence does not seem to be at all correct. That is, we disagree that full recognition of the gain or loss at the time of the sale and leaseback transaction should not be made. This situation, it seems to us, is a vision of an environment where the buyer

will not have economic benefits and bargaining power in defining the contract price. Thus, the seller-lessee will guide the sale. The buyer, for example, may be compelled to carry out the transaction due to: (i) tax benefits, as evidenced in Alvayay, Rutherford and Smith (1995); (ii) operational advantages associated with an operation in which the buyer has long-term contractual security as to the lessee of its operation (Sirmans & Slade, 2010); (iii) increase in the wealth of shareholders of companies that engage in leaseback transactions since there is evidence that these transactions have significant positive effects on the companies' share prices (Fisher, 2004; Elayan, Meyer & Li, 2006; Grönlund, Louko & Vaihekoski, 2008; Wells & Whitby, 2012).

In situations of economic equilibrium between seller and buyer, Sirmans and Slade (2010) indicate that even though it is a sale followed by a leaseback, it contains the economic substance, according to the criteria of IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers. This fact could support the full recognition of the gain.

Thus, we suggest that the right-of-use asset acquired in a sale-leaseback transaction should be measured at the fair value of the asset on the date of the transaction and that this should, from then on, be the base value for calculating the depreciation and consequent impairment loss, as usually is the case with revaluations of property, plant and equipment, in accordance with IAS 16. In cases where it is impossible to measure fair value, whether for economic or even regulatory reasons, we should follow the same measurement criteria already defined for the other lease cases. That is, consider the amount negotiated in the lease as a proxy for the fair value.

We believe that the pronouncement should standardize the treatment in both cases (leaseback and lease in general). If it is important to use fair value when comparing the present value of the contract's consideration for the leaseback, why not use the same criterion for the lease? Another point (paragraph 100 A) is regarding the details of payments related to the right to use the lease asset: fixed and variable payments (regardless of whether they depend on an index or a rate). We believe that the amounts that should comprise the right to use asset and the lease liability in the case of the leaseback should follow what is defined for the commercial lease, in general.

We believe that the change may increase the possibility of choosing criteria, which cannot be verified by the information users, even if disclosed in explanatory notes. Besides, a differentiation is created between leases' treatment with and without sale-leaseback, as pointed out, without any economic justification.

Question 2—Transition (paragraph C20E of the [Draft] amendment to IFRS 16)

Paragraph C20E of the [Draft] amendment to IFRS 16 proposes that a seller-lessee apply the [Draft] amendment to IFRS 16 retrospectively in accordance with IAS 8 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors to sale and leaseback transactions entered into after the date of initial application of IFRS 16. However, if retrospective application to a sale and leaseback transaction that includes variable lease payments is possible only with the use of hindsight, the seller-lessee would determine the expected lease payments for that transaction at the beginning of the annual reporting period in which it first applies the amendment.

Do you agree with this proposal? Why or why not? If you disagree with the proposal, please explain what you suggest instead and why.

We agree that there is a retrospective bias, and we overestimated the ability to forecast variable payments at the beginning of the contract in subsequent periods. The professionals heard by the study group understand that, despite this, the best form of treatment in the transition would not be retrospective treatment. Such treatment makes the process much more complex. Therefore, it is suggested to treat the transition prospectively, simplifying the registration for accounting information preparers. The transition's effect could be demonstrated in the Notes, without prejudice to information availability for financial statements' users.

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DECLARAÇÃO DO ESTRATO DO PTT.

Transformação causada pelo produto técnico/tecnológico no ambiente (organização, comunidade, localidade, etc.) ao qual se destina. Necessário declarar o motivo da criação, a relevância da questão do demandante e o foco de aplicação do produto. Avalia-se o impacto potencial e realizado do produto ao ambiente de transformação ao que se destina.											
Critério de avaliação	Realizado			Potencial			Replicável			TOTAL	
	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Pontos	Pond.
IMPACTO (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Ausência de impacto	10	6,0	Pontos Ausência de impacto	10,0	4				10,0	16,7
APLICABILIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Não aplicada	10	4,0	Pontos Não aplicável	10,0	2	Pontos Não Replicável	10	4,0	10,0	16,7
INOVAÇÃO (Peso: 25%)	Sem inovação	15	15,0							15,0	25,0
COMPLEXIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Não complexo	10	10,0							10,0	16,7
							Estrato	TA2	Pontuação		75,0